

Mannich Bases Derived from 5-(2', 4', 5'-Trichlorophenoxy-methyl)-1, 3, 4-Oxadiazol-2-Thione

H. N. PANDEY, LALLAN MISHRA and VISHNU JI RAM*

Department of Chemistry, S. C. College, Balia (U.P.)

Manuscript received 26 March 1976, revised 24 November 1976, accepted 26 November 1976

Starting from 5-(2', 4', 5'-trichlorophenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione, new Mannich bases were synthesised by the action of formaldehyde and different aryl/heterocyclic amines. The structures were elucidated by spectral studies. Some compounds were found to be active fungicides.

A SURVEY of literature reveals that derivatives of 5-substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-one and their thio analogues are highly active against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*¹⁻³. Oxadiazoles are also known to exhibit hypoglycemic⁴, carcinostatic⁵, bacterostatic⁶, antiviral⁷ and antifungal⁸ properties. In our earlier communications⁹⁻¹¹, we have reported the synthesis, structure and biological activity of Mannich bases derived from 5-substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones.

Kubo *et al.*¹² observed that inclusion of halophenoxy-methyl moiety at position five of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles enhances their herbicidal properties. The Mannich reaction has, therefore, been extended with 5-(2',4',5'-trichlorophenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (I) with the hope that the newly synthesised Mannich bases (II) might exhibit enhanced fungicidal activity due to 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxy-methyl moiety.

The IR spectra of the compounds (II) exhibit the presence of sharp and intense peaks in the region 1050-1090 cm^{-1} , which are characteristic of $>\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching vibrations, while strong peaks at 1360 and 1385 cm^{-1} are attributed to CN stretching frequency. A very strong peak near 700 cm^{-1} is attributed to C-Cl stretching vibrations while peaks around 820, 780 cm^{-1} are due to C-H bending vibrations (out of plane). Sharp and strong peaks at 1590 and 1645 cm^{-1} are due to C-H bending vibrations (in plane); bands at 3050, 2920 and 2850 cm^{-1} are supposed due to C-H stretching vibrations.

Experimental

All the m.p.s. were taken in open capillary tube and are uncorrected.

3-Diphenylaminomethyl-5-(2', 4', 5'-trichlorophenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione : 5-(2', 4', 5'-trichlorophenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione¹³ (3.0g, 0.01

The Mannich bases were prepared by reacting compound (I) with formaldehyde and different aromatic as well as heterocyclic amines. The starting material (I) was synthesised from 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetohydrazide by the method of Young and Wood¹³ in 75% yield. It has been noted that while aromatic amine reacts instantly, the heterocyclic amines take 3-4 hr for the completion of the reaction.

mole) in ethanol was treated with formaldehyde (2 ml, 40%). To this mixture, an ethanolic solution of diphenyl amine (1.94 g, 0.01 mole) was added dropwise with stirring. The mixture was kept in refrigerator overnight. A crystalline solid precipitated which was filtered and crystallised with aqueous ethanol, m.p. 95°. *Anal.* Found : N, 8.8; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{Cl}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$: N, 8.52%.

Other Mannich bases prepared in this series are reported in Table 1 along with their physical data.

3-(α -Pyridylaminomethyl)-5-(2', 4', 5'-trichlorophenoxy-methyl)-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione : To a mixture of

* Present Address : Department of Chemistry, Konstanz University, West Germany.

TABLE I—THE ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND YIELD OF MANNICH BASES (II)

S.No.	R	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	N %	
					Found	Calcd.
1	Phenyl	60	148	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₂ S	10.08	10.09
2	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	70	160	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl ₃ BrO ₂ S	10.86	9.73
3	<i>p</i> -Carboxylphenyl	62	135	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₄ S	10.41	9.13
4	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	63	122	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₂ S	10.41	9.77
5	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	58	136	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₂ S	10.50	9.77
6	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	65	202	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₂ S	10.20	9.77
7	<i>o</i> -Phenetyl	—	Oily	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₂ S	—	9.13
8	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	—	Oily	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₃ S	—	9.42
9	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	50	205	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₃ S	9.50	9.42
10	<i>p</i> -(<i>n</i> -)Butylcarboxylatephenyl	63	128	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₄ S	8.30	8.14
11	<i>p</i> -Acetylphenyl	70	185	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₃ S	10.12	9.17
12	2,4,5-Trichlorophenyl	65	170	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₂ Cl ₆ O ₂ S	8.12	8.08
12	2,4,6-Trichlorophenyl	—	Oily	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₂ Cl ₆ O ₂ S	—	8.08
14	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	70	160	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ Cl ₃ O ₂ S	12.20	12.19
15	<i>p</i> -(<i>iso</i>)Butylcarboxylatephenyl	—	Gummy	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ Cl ₃ O ₄ S	—	8.14

compound (I; 2.0 g) and formaldehyde (1.5 ml, 40%) in ethanol, 2-aminopyridine (0.7 g) in little ethanol was added dropwise with stirring. The reaction mixture was left in refrigerator for 2 days with occasional shaking. The white crystalline solid which separated was filtered and later on crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 162°, yield 60%. *Anal.* Found: N, 13.41; Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₄Cl₃O₂S: N, 13.56%.

3-(5'-Phenyl thiazol-2'-aminomethyl)-5-(2', 4', 5'-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione: Compound (I, 2.0 g) was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) and to this was added formaldehyde (1.5 ml). To this mixture was added a solution of 2-amino-5-phenyl thiazole (1.3 g) with stirring. The whole mixture was kept in refrigerator for 24 hr. A gummy solid separated which solidified on addition of petroleum ether (40°-60°) and later on crystallised with aqueous ethanol, m.p. 110°, yield, 65%. *Anal.* Found: N, 11.18. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₃N₄Cl₃O₂S₂: N, 11.2%.

3-(5'-Phenyl-1", 3", 4"-oxadiazol-2"-aminomethyl)-5-(2', 4', 5'-trichloro phenoxyethyl)-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione: To a mixture of compound (I, 2.0 g) and formaldehyde (1.8 ml, 40%) in methanol (10 ml), was added 2 amino 5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (1.1 g) dropwise with stirring. The reaction mixture was kept in refrigerator overnight. A crystalline precipitate was obtained which was crystallised with ethanolic dimethyl formamide mixture, m.p. 135°d, yield 40%. *Anal.* Found: N, 14.52. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂N₅Cl₃O₃S: N, 14.4%.

Fungicidal activity: All the compounds were tested for their fungicidal activity against *Aspergillus niger* by Agar plate technique¹⁴ at three different concentrations, namely 1 : 1000, 1 : 10,000, 1 : 100,000. The number of replications was three. It was observed that fungicidal activity increases as the number of halogen atoms increases in the compounds. Maximum fungus control was observed with 3-(2',4',5"-trichlorophenylaminomethyl)-5-(2',4',

5'-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione probably due to larger number of chlorine atoms.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head of the Chemistry Department, Gorakhpur University for his keen interest and encouragement and to Dr. Nitya Nand, Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for micro analyses and IR spectra of the compounds. Thanks are also due to the authorities of the institution for providing necessary facilities. The financial assistance granted by U.G.C. to one of us (H.N.P.) also gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. A. E. WILDERSMITH and E. FROMMEL, *Arzneimittel Forsch.*, 1962, 12, 22, 275, 485; U.S. Pat. 2,758,117 (1956); *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 52, 3670.
2. H. C. CALDWELL, R. J. SEIWALD and J. H. BURKHALTER, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Edn.*, 1958, 47, 799.
3. I. MUR, M. T. SIDDIQUI and A. M. COMRIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 2798.
4. J. B. O'NEAL, H. ROSEN, P. B. RUSSEL, A. C. ADAMS and A. BLUMENTHAL, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, 5, 617.
5. J. J. OLESON, A. SLOBODA and W. P. TROY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 6713.
6. O. HÜBNER, U.S. Pat. 2,447,702 (1948); *Chem. Abs.*, 1948, 42, 8823.
7. D. J. JONES, R. SLACK, S. SQUIRES and K. R. H. WOODBRIDGE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1963, 8, 676.
8. L. R. BELLON, French Pat. 1,273,881 (1962); *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 57, 9860.
9. V. J. RAM and H. N. PANDEY, *Agr. Biol. Chem.*, 1973, 37, 1465.
10. V. J. RAM and H. N. PANDEY, *Agr. Biol. Chem.*, 1973, 37, 2191.
11. V. J. RAM and H. N. PANDEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 231.
12. H. KUBO *et al.*, *Zassho Kenkyu (Japan)*, 1969, 8, 426.
13. R. W. YOUNG and K. H. WOOD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 400.
14. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 11, 357.